

Scaled boundary finite element based method for crack initiation and propagation in fiber reinforced composite structures

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Introduction

Scaled Boundary Finite Element Method (SBFEM)

- SBFEM is a semi-analytical tool in which circumferential direction is solved numerically while the radial direction is solved analytically. Hence it provides the more accurate solutions with smaller number of nodes.
- SBFEM offers ease and flexibility to mesh any given domain. The domain is divided into polygonal subdomains and boundary of each subdomain is discretised into line elements. Thus, the discretisation process reduces by one spatial dimension. No restrictions are imposed on number of sides in a subdomain or number of line elements on a side.
- SBFEM captures the stress singularity at the crack tip without any mesh refinement.

Crack Initiation Scheme

- Location of the first crack**
 - Maximum stress failure criterion** - Occurrence of maximum value of failure index will determine the location of the first formed crack.

Longitudinal failure index = $\frac{\sigma_1}{X_1}$ (Fibre breaking)

Transverse failure index = $\frac{\sigma_2}{X_2}$ (Matrix Cracking)

(X_i is the tensile strength in 'i' direction)
- Direction of the first formed crack**
 - Normal stress ratio criterion** - Angle at which stress ratio σ_b/X_b achieves a maximum, will be the direction of the crack, where $X_b = X_1 \sin^2 \theta + X_2 \cos^2 \theta$.
 - Minimum strain energy density criterion** - Angle at which strain energy density ($= \frac{1}{2}[\sigma]^T[\epsilon] = \frac{1}{2}[\sigma]^T[D]^{-1}[\sigma]$) at a distance 'r' achieves a minimum, will be the direction of the crack.

Numerical Example

Problem Statement

Material Properties (CFRP composites)
 $E_1 = 120$ GPa
 $E_2 = 12$ GPa
 $\nu_{12} = 0.25$
 $G_{12} = 3$ GPa
 Fibre angle = 45°
 $X_1 = 3$ GPa
 $X_2 = 500$ Mpa
 $p = 100$ MPa

Location of crack initiation

- Maximum value is observed in case of transverse failure index, hence the damage will be dominated by matrix cracking.
- Location of crack initiation is identified at an angle of $\sim 40^\circ$ measured counter clockwise at the centre of the semicircle.

*Failure indices are set to zero when stresses are compressive (i.e. negative)

Adopted meshing

- Simplified mesh is required in case of SBFEM as compared to FEM. Body is needed to be divided into two domains only.
- Nodal density is kept higher at the semi-circular boundary because it is the most probable region for the damage initiation

Direction of crack initiation

Conclusions

- SBFEM proves to be a better tool for crack initiation studies as it offers more accurate solutions with lesser mesh requirements which in turn increases computational performance.
- Normal stress ratio criterion predicts the crack parallel to the fibers, which is mostly observed in case of unidirectional plies; however, minimum strain energy density criterion fails to acceptable outcome.
- After identifying the location and the direction of the first formed crack, crack propagation can be modelled easily using the available criteria in the literature.

Future Work

- Investigation will be extended from orthotropic materials to laminated composite structures and SBFEM will be employed to study damage evolution in this regard.

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